

Description of Ulvales from the coast of Harihareshwar, Dist. Raigad, Maharashtra, India

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ABSTRACT

The present study encompasses the systematic collection, morphological characterization, and anatomical investigation of marine algae belonging to the division Chlorophyta, order Ulvales, sourced from the rocky intertidal and subtidal zones along the coast of Shri Harihareshwar, Raigad District, Maharashtra, India. During the course of this investigation, three distinct species of the genus *Ulva* were collected, identified, and documented, namely *Ulva lactuca* L., *Ulva fasciata* Delile, and *Ulva intestinalis* L. The species were identified based on their morphological and anatomical characters and confirmed using standard taxonomic literature. This study adds to the knowledge of phycological diversity of the Raigad coast and serves as a reference for future studies on marine Chlorophyta of this region.

Keywords: Ulvales, *Ulva lactuca*, *Ulva fasciata*, *Ulva intestinalis*, Harihareshwar coast, Konkan coast.

INTRODUCTION

The earliest record of marine algae from the Maharashtra coast dates back to Kirtikar (1886), who reported marine algae collected from the Ratnagiri coast, as later documented by Deodhar (1987). Early taxonomic investigations of Indian marine algae were primarily based on morphological and anatomical criteria. Foundational works by Iyengar (1927) established the basis of Indian marine phycology by providing detailed descriptions of green algae and diagnostic taxonomic features. Ramanathan (1939) further contributed to the taxonomy and distribution of the genus *Ulva* along Indian coasts. Srinivasan (1946) expanded early floristic knowledge of marine algae from Indian coastal regions. Subsequent contributions by Krishnamurthy (1967), Sarma and Suryanarayana (1967), Dixit (1968), and Rao and Sreeramulu (1970) significantly advanced taxonomic understanding and distributional records of marine algae, including members of Chlorophyta. Joshi and Krishnamurthy (1972) reported the occurrence and taxonomy of tubular *Ulva* species from Indian coastal waters. Regional surveys by Untawale and Dhargalkar (1975) and Agadi and Untawale (1978) documented seaweed diversity along the Goa coast, while Untawale et al. (1979) reported 94 species of seaweeds from the Maharashtra coast, providing

important baseline floristic data. Untawale (1983) documented seaweed diversity along the Maharashtra coast and emphasized the ecological distribution of intertidal marine algae. Chennubhotla et al. (1988) and Desikachary et al. (1990) provided comprehensive accounts of Indian seaweeds, emphasizing morphological and anatomical features such as thallus organization, cellular structure, and reproductive characteristics as essential taxonomic criteria. Rao et al. (1993) and Kaliaperumal et al. (1998) further expanded taxonomic knowledge and regional distribution records of marine algae along Indian coasts. Malta et al. (1999), Tan et al. (1999), and Littler and Littler (2000) described morphological variability and structural characteristics of *Ulva*, including blade-like and tubular forms, and emphasized the challenges associated with morphological identification.

Oza and Zaidi (2000, 2001) published a revised checklist documenting approximately 844 marine algal species from Indian waters, including 159 species from the Maharashtra coast. Dhargalkar and Deshmukh (1996) and Dhargalkar et al. (2001) further documented macroalgal diversity along the west coast of Maharashtra. Blomster et al. (2002) demonstrated that environmental factors such as salinity, nutrient availability, and hydrodynamic stress significantly influence *Ulva* morphology, complicating species-level identification. Sahoo et al. (2003), James (2004), Venkataraman (2005), Rath and Adhikary (2006, 2007), and Rao and Mantri (2006) contributed to expanded knowledge of marine algal diversity along Indian coasts. These studies collectively indicated that approximately 624 species of seaweeds had been recorded from Indian coastal waters.

Floristic and taxonomic surveys continued to improve systematic understanding of Indian marine algae. Jha et al. (2009) provided updated distributional records and identification keys for Indian seaweeds. Kaladharan et al. (2011) and Pereira and Almeida (2012, 2014) contributed additional taxonomic documentation of *Ulva* species. Ecological studies by Ye et al. (2011) and Liu et al. (2013) documented rapid proliferation of *Ulva* species in nutrient-enriched coastal waters, commonly referred to as “green tides,” highlighting their ecological adaptability and environmental significance. Bast et al. (2014) and Kazi et al. (2016) described new species of *Ulva* from Indian coasts using morphological and taxonomic

criteria. Rao and Gupta (2015) reported that the genus *Ulva* is represented by approximately 31 taxa in India.

More recent biodiversity assessments and taxonomic investigations have further strengthened systematic knowledge of Indian seaweeds. Kamboj et al. (2019) and Mantri et al. (2019) emphasized the ecological, economic, and biotechnological importance of marine macroalgae, including their applications as food, biofertilizers, and sources of bioactive compounds. Palanisamy and Kumar (2020) and Aron and Palanisamy (2021) provided updated accounts of the taxonomy, distribution, and diversity of *Ulva* species from Indian coastal habitats. Guiry and Guiry (2023) confirmed the cosmopolitan distribution and taxonomic significance of the genus *Ulva* based on global systematic databases. In addition, specialized accounts of the Maharashtra coast document the occurrence of a significant regional flora, with systematic records indicating around 240 marine algal species belonging to 102 genera and 46 families from this state’s coast, reflecting substantial local biodiversity (Piwalatkar, 2025). The present study therefore aims to systematically collect, identify, and document members of Ulvales from the Harihareshwar coast which reflects in the contributing baseline taxonomic data of the order Ulvales from the study area.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Marine algal specimens were collected from the rocky intertidal region of Harihareshwar, Raigad District, Maharashtra, situated along the Konkan coast of India. The coastline is characterized by lateritic rocky platforms and tidal pools that support diverse macroalgal communities. Sampling was conducted during low tide, and thalli were carefully detached along with their holdfasts to preserve structural integrity. Samples were rinsed with seawater in the field to remove adhering debris and transported to the laboratory in clean polythene bags containing seawater.

In the laboratory, specimens were washed with distilled water and examined for macroscopic characters such as thallus colour, texture, size, blade thickness, and mode of attachment. For anatomical analysis, thin transverse sections of fresh thalli were prepared manually, mounted in glycerine, and observed under a compound light microscope. Cellular

features including thallus organization, cell arrangement, chloroplast morphology, and presence of pyrenoids were recorded.

Representative specimens were preserved as herbarium sheets following standard procedures and deposited in the Department of Botany. Species identification was carried out using standard literature.

RESULTS

1. *Ulva intestinalis* L.

Light greenish to Green, long, tubular, filaments intestine like, holdfast minute, discoidal. Fronds proliferated, thin, cylindrical below and becoming inflated and irregularly constricted above. Thalli measured of 2 cm to 9.5 cm in length and 2 mm to 4 mm in width., Cells length 17 to 21µm & Cell width 12 to 14µm. Cell in surface view rounded to polygonal, thin, single layer, chloroplast distributed through cell.

2. *Ulva fasciata* Delile

Dark-light green, leafy, ribbon shaped, foliaceous, simple, branched. Fronds leafy, deeply divided into several linear blades, uniformly flattened, surface smooth, membranous, irregularly lobed, gradually tapering towards apex; margins entire to frequently undulate, apex acute to obtuse. Thalli measured of 14 cm to 20 cm in length and 2 cm to 3 cm in width. Cells length 20 to 26 µm & Cell width 12 to 16 µm. Cells in surface view polygonal - squarish, distromatic, compactly arranged, uninucleate with chloroplast towards outward side of cells.

3. *Ulva lactuca* L.

Light-dark green, lettuce type, membranous, rosette like, discoidal holdfast, thin with several lobes, margins undulated, wavy, apex obtuse. Thalli measured of 7 cm to 9.5 cm in length and 5 cm to 7cm in width. Cells length 14 to 20µm & Cell width 16 to 22µm. Cells rectangular, uninucleate, sections nearly square or taller than broad.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Ulva intestinalis exhibited a hollow, tubular, monostromatic thallus measuring Thalli measured of 2 cm to 9.5 cm in length and 2 mm to 4 mm in width., with small polygonal cells Cells length 17 to 21µm &

Cell width 12 to 14µm arranged in a single layer. In contrast.

U. fasciata was characterized by ribbon-like, distromatic blades of 14 cm to 20 cm in length and 2 cm to 3 cm in width., with comparatively larger cells measuring length 20 to 26 µm & Cell width 12 to 16 µm.

U. lactuca showed a broad, foliose, distromatic thallus reaching 7 cm to 9.5 cm in length and 5 cm to 7cm in width. and quadrangular cells measuring Cells length 14 to 20µm & Cell width 16 to 22µm.

Key to the species	
Thallus tubular and hollow rarely branched and TS of thallus is single layer; chloroplast distributed through cell	<i>U. intestinalis</i>
Thallus not tubular but flatten	2
Thallus leafy, deeply divided into several narrow linear blades, uniformly flattened, surface smooth, membranous, irregularly lobed, gradually tapering towards apex; cells in transverse sections nearly square, chloroplast towards outward side of cells	<i>U. fasciata</i>
Thallus not leafy or deeply divided into several narrow linear blades, gradually tapering towards apex	3
Thallus / Blades not naturally perforate; cells in transverse sections nearly square or taller than broad	<i>U. lactuca</i>

Transverse sections confirmed the monostromatic condition in *U. intestinalis* and distromatic structure in *U. lactuca* and *U. fasciata*. The occurrence of these species indicates their adaptation to wave-exposed, nutrient-influenced coastal habitats of the Konkan region. The present study confirms the occurrence of three *Ulva* species i.e., *Ulva intestinalis*, *Ulva fasciata*, and *Ulva Lactuca* from the rocky intertidal region of Harihareshwar, Maharashtra.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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